

N-bromosalicylideneanthranilic acid complexes of Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II)⁴ etc were recently prepared. In this preliminary communication we report the synthesis of several metal complexes of Schiff bases derived from vanillin and anthranilic acid or bromoanthranilic acid. It may be mentioned that this is the first report on the metal complexes of these ligands and we wish to make a comprehensive study of the co-ordination complexes of these ligands with various transition metal ions.

Preparation of Vanillideneanthranilic Acid :

A mixture of alcoholic solution of vanillin (1.52 g) and anthranilic acid (1.36 g) was refluxed for 1 hour. It was allowed to cool, water was added and the solution was left overnight in a refrigerator for crystallisation. Fine shining yellow crystals which were separated, were recrystallised from 1 : 1 ethanol and preserved in a vacuum desiccator. m.p. 174°.

Metal Complexes : These were prepared by refluxing a mixture of the metal chloride and the ligand in appropriate molar ratio in suitable solvents for about 5-6 hours. The solid complexes were filtered, washed with dry ethanol or ethyl acetate and dried in vacuum desiccator. Since most of these complexes have a low solubility in common organic solvents they were purified by subjecting to Soxhlet extraction in dry ethanol and dried in vacuum.

Based on elemental analysis the metal complexes display 1 : 2 or 1 : 1 stoichiometry and may possess the composition ML_2X_2 or $(MLX)_2$. The magnetic moments indicate the presence of 3, 2 and 1 unpaired electrons in Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) and the remaining complexes were found to be diamagnetic. From these values it is apparent that Ti, Zr, Hf and Th complexes possess monomeric octahedral structure whereas the remaining planar complexes may exist as dimers. Negligibly small conductance values of the compounds suggest them to be non-electrolytes.

The presence of the $\nu(OH)$ stretch in the infra-red spectra of the complexes indicate the monobasic character of the ligands. In the complexes $\nu C=O$ and $\nu C=N$ were shifted to lower frequency side due to complexation. As the complexes are insoluble in common solvents it was not possible to find out molecular weights and degree of polymerisation of the complexes.

Further studies in N.M.R., E.P.R., T.G.A., etc. are in progress and details will be reported in due course.

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Complexes of Cu(II) and Cd(II) with Tetradentate Schiff's Bases

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WE have been trying to synthesize new polydentate ligands in order to achieve rare co-ordination numbers through complexation of these ligands with some common divalent metal ions. In our earlier attempts, we have reported¹⁻⁴ complexes of a tridentate ligand, tri and tetradentate Schiff's bases using benzoin as the basic nucleus. In the present communication we have extended our investigation to the preparation of Cu(II) and Cd(II) complexes with tetradentate Schiff's bases derived from benzoin and ethylenediamine and *o*-phenylenediamine.

The method of preparation of the Schiff's bases have been mentioned in our earlier communication. Ethanolic solution of Cu(II) and Cd(II) chlorides were reacted with the Schiff's bases in 1 : 1 ratio followed by dropwise addition of ammonia with constant stirring when metal chelates separated out. These are filtered, washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried *in vacuo*.

Metal and nitrogen were estimated by standard methods. Conductance was measured in M/1000 acetone solution using Toshniwal conductivity Bridge. Magnetic susceptibility was measured on the solid specimen by Gouy method. IR spectra were recorded on KBr phase using Beckman IR-12 spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra were recorded on a Hilgerwatt uvispeck spectrophotometer with M/100 (Chloroform ligand) solution of the complexes. The relevant analytical conductance

and magnetic susceptibility data are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1—M.P. ANALYSIS, CONDUCTANCE AND MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY DATA

Compound	M.P. °C	%metal		%Nitrogen		Λ_M Ohm ⁻¹ cm ²	μ_{eff} B.M.
		Found	Reqd	Found	Reqd		
[CuL]	174	12.15	12.46	5.34	5.49	8.0	1.78
[CuL']	158	11.07	11.89	4.86	5.02	8.5	1.75
[CdL]	197	19.82	20.13	4.89	5.01	9.0	—
[CdL']	184	18.29	18.53	4.37	4.61	10.5	—

LH₂ and L'H₂ = Schiff's bases derived from benzoin and ethylenediamine and *o*-phenylenediamine respectively.

Results and Discussion

Complexes reported in the present investigation have the composition [ML] and [ML'] where M = Cu(II), Cd(II) and LH₂ and L'H₂ are Schiff's bases derived from benzoin with ethylenediamine and *o*-phenylenediamine respectively. Copper complexes are green and cadmium complexes are white in colour. All the four complexes have low melting points and are fairly soluble in acetone, having low conductance values (Table 1) indicating non-electrolytic nature of the complexes.

The Schiff's bases can function as tetradentate ligands using two hydroxyl oxygens and two imino nitrogen atoms as the bonding sites. Assignments have been made for the two principal bands, i.e. $\nu(C-O)$ and $\nu(C=N)$ in the IR spectrum. In the ligands the appearance of a band at 1210 cm⁻¹ due to $\nu(C-O)$ has shifted down to 1200 cm⁻¹ in the complexes. The $\nu(C=N)$ band has appeared at 1600 and 1590 cm⁻¹ which has shifted to lower frequency region for complexes [ML] and to higher frequency region for complexes of the type [ML']. However, conclusive evidence regarding the bonding of nitrogen and oxygen atoms have been provided by occurrence of $\nu(M-N)$ and $\nu(M-O)$ around 515 and ~440 cm⁻¹ respectively in the complexes⁵.

In the electronic spectra of Cu(II) complexes one broad band appears around 15000 region indicating a planar configuration for these complexes. Magnetic moment values of the Cu(II) complexes indicate the presence of one unpaired electron. From the analysis conductance and IR spectral studies of Cd(II) complexes are found to be four co-ordinated having a tetrahedral environment around the metal ions.

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Study of Camoquin-Ferrous Sulphate Complex

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CAMOQUIN is more active than quinine against malaria. In continuation of our work¹⁻⁴ on the metal complexes of antimalarials, herein we describe camoquin-ferrous sulphate complex.

Experimental

Composition of the Complex :

(a) Standard solutions of ferrous sulphate (0.01 M) and camoquin base (0.005 M) were prepared in spectroscopically pure 80% methanol. 5 ml of the ligand was diluted to 200 ml and titrated against the metal solution using 'Toshniwal' conductivity bridge and dip type electrodes at 19°. The analysis of conductance data reveals that a 1 : 2 complex is formed in solution.

(b) The nature of the complex was studied spectrophotometrically on 'Spekol' using Vosburgh and Cooper⁵ Method. Mixtures containing 2 : 1, 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 proportions of equimolar solutions of ferrous sulphate and camoquin (5×10^{-4} M) in spectroscopically pure methanol were taken. The plot of absorbance vs wavelength is given in Fig. 1.

(c) Formation of 1 : 2 complex was further confirmed by the following :

- (i) Job's Method⁶,
- (ii) Mole ratio Method⁷ and
- (iii) Slope ratio Method⁸.

Isolation and Analysis :

Camoquin base 1.0 g (1 M) was dissolved in methyl alcohol and ferrous sulphate 1.56 g (2 M) was dissolved in minimum quantity of methyl alcohol with two drops of sulphuric acid were mixed slowly to ferrous sulphate solution with constant stirring when a chocolate coloured complex was obtained immediately. It was cooled in an ice bath for four hours, filtered, washed with methyl alcohol and dried on porous plate ; yield 1.7 g. No attempt was made to prepare 1 : 1 complex.

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